

Study of interactions between a novel elastomer and solvents

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The flexibility parameters of chlorosulfonated polyethylene indicate chain stiffness comparable to other synthetic elastomers. Similar conclusion is also reached from a study of the hydrodynamic behavior. The Mark-Houwink constants, obtained from the molecular weight dependence of $[\eta]$, also indicate a fairly coiled up configuration for the molecular chain. The parameters characterizing the stiffness of the elastomer chain, such as the effective bond length (b), the steric factor (σ) also reveal that the chlorosulfonated polyethylene chain resembles the other elastomers so far as the chain flexibility is concerned. Unperturbed dimension values obtained from θ -solvent data and other theories of dilute polymer solutions show good agreement with each other.

Interactions between elastomers and solvents may cause localized disruption of intermolecular cohesive forces. These resemble to the interactions of other polymers and solvents. The interaction causes structural rearrangements. Studies of polymer-solvent interactions have been quite exhaustive, and numerous investigations have been carried out. Studies on elastomers such as butyl¹, polyisoprene (natural rubber)², polybutadiene^{3,4}, synthetic polyisoprene⁵, poly(diphenylmethyl methacrylate)⁶, poly(2,6-dimethylphenyl methacrylate)⁷, poly(styrene)-block-poly(butadiene)-block(styrene)⁸, polyisobutene⁹, poly(octadecyl methacrylate)¹⁰, poly(*p*-tert-butylstyrene)¹¹, poly(monododecyl itaconate)¹², poly(di-*n*-hexylsilane)¹³, polyisobutylene¹⁴, poly(butylene adipate-co-butylene isophthalate)¹⁵, poly(2-acrylamino-2-methylpropane sulfonamide)¹⁶, cellulose diacetate¹⁷ and poly(dimethyl siloxane)¹⁸ have been recently published. However, relatively little is known about the properties of chlorosulfonated polyethylene.

The present work was undertaken to investigate the behavior of chlorosulfonated polyethylene in dilute solution and to correlate the data in terms of their fundamental molecular parameters. The present investigation aims at a clear understanding of the solution properties of chlorosulfonated polyethylene and elucidation of their configurations and chain flexibilities. Precision measurement of various hydrodynamic and configurational parameters of this polymer was one of the purpose of this work, but one main object was to gather from these data a comprehensive knowledge about the molecular behavior of chlorosulfonated polyethylene in dilute solution.

Results and Discussion

In our previous communication¹⁹, the Mark-Houwink equation of chlorosulfonated polyethylene leads to $[\eta]$

$= 5.2481 \times 10^{-4} M_w^{0.56}$. The ν -value of 0.56 for the polymer in toluene indicates a low hydrodynamic volume and a tightly coiled structure. To analyze the data shown in Table 1 it can be stated that chlorosulfonated polyethylene in toluene is more tightly coiled than natural rubber in toluene^{2,22},

Table 1

Polymer	Temp. °C	Solvent	ν	$K' \times 10^5$	Mol. wt. range $\times 10^{-4}$	Method*, Ref.
Chlorosulfonated polyethylene	25	Toluene	0.56	52.481	6-331	Present work L. S. O. S.
Natural rubber	25	Toluene	0.667	50.2	7-100	22
Polybutadiene (70% <i>trans</i> , 4% <i>cis</i> , 25% 1,2)	25	Cyclohexane	0.77	12.0	230-800	30
Polychloroprene (Neoprene C.G)	25	Benzene	0.89	2.02	6-150	O. S. 24
Polyisobutylene	0	Toluene	0.60	40.0	7-150	O. S. 25

*O.S. = mol. wt. determination by osmotic pressure; L.S. = mol. wt. determination by light scattering.

polybutadiene in cyclohexane^{4,23}, polychloroprene in benzene²⁴ and polyisobutylene in toluene^{14,25}. The $[\eta]$ - M relations on the basis of various modes²⁰ have been explained. The results indicate a high degree of coiling, resulting in solvent immobilizing behavior. The relationship between M_w and intrinsic viscosity at the theta-point²¹ corresponds to $[\eta]_0 = 0.912 \times 10^{-3} M_w^{0.5}$. The expansion factor (α_n) evaluated from viscometric measurement shows a weak dependence on molecular weight.

The Flory constant (ϕ_0) is independent of the solvent and the polymer. For the present experiment it is found to be 1.96×10^{21} which is slightly lower than Flory's original value of $2.1-2.2 \times 10^{21}$. Flory²⁶ reported that the value decreases systematically with decreasing molecular weight. Most synthetic polymers have smaller values subject to polydispersity²⁷.

The effective bond length (b) for chlorosulfonated polyethylene was calculated from the relation,

$$b = [\bar{R}_0^2 / (\text{D.P.})]^{1/2} = [K / (q_z \phi_0)]^{1/2} m_0^{1/2} \times 10^8$$

where $(\bar{R}_0^2)^{1/2}$ is root-mean square end-to-end distance at θ condition and K the constant term of the Flory-Fox equation as $[\eta]_\theta = KM^{1/2}$ and q_z the appropriate correction factor for most probable distribution. The value obtained for the present polymer in toluene is 8.57 Å. The value lies in between the value of 7.99 exhibited by gutta purcha in *n*-propyl acetate^{2,28} and 8.6, the value for polystyrene in toluene²⁹. The present value is higher than the value 6.02 for polybutadiene in benzene^{4,30}, 7.6, the value for polychloroprene in benzene³¹ and 6.7, the value for polyisoprene (Hevea) in benzene^{2,32}. This implies that the chlorosulfonated polyethylene in toluene is stiffer than polybutadiene in benzene.

The steric factor (σ) serves as an index to the hindrance to freedom of rotation about the chain bonds. For chlorosulfonated polyethylene it is found to be 1.48 which is higher than polychloroprene in benzene (85% *trans*)³¹, gutta purcha in *n*-propyl acetate (100% *trans*)²⁸ but lower than the value of polybutadiene in benzene (92% *cis*)³⁰ and polyisoprene in benzene (100% *cis*)²⁸.

The persistence length is conceptually defined as the average projection of an infinitely long chain along the direction of its first link. For a chain with free internal rotations persistence length (q) is evaluated as $q = l / (1 - \cos \theta)$, where l is the bond length and θ the supplement of the valence bond angle; while for real chains this must be replaced by $q = \sigma^2 l / (1 - \cos \theta)$. The value obtained for chlorosulfonated polyethylene is 5.05. The present value indicates a more flexible behavior than other elastomers³³ like natural rubber, polyisoprene, gutta purcha, polystyrene, nylon 66 and polyethylene.

The size of macromolecules (dimension) in solution cannot strictly be defined because a single molecular coil alters in shape with time and these conformational changes are due to Brownian motion. The molecular size varies from molecule to molecule of identical mass and structure, and it can only be described in terms of average properties. Perturbed dimensions are the chain dimensions in a given sol-

vent where intermolecular interactions between macromolecules and solvent occur. Unperturbed dimensions are the chain dimensions in a given solvent determined solely by bond length and angles. The unperturbed dimensions of a linear polymer chain ($\bar{r}_0^2$ or $\bar{s}_0^2$) vary with molecular weight. Values of the type $(\bar{r}_0^2 / M)$ or $(\bar{s}_0^2 / M)$ depend on chain structure and not upon a solvent or temperature. The unperturbed chain dimension of chlorosulfonated polyethylene is calculated from theta-solvent data by the relation,

$$[\eta]_0 = KM^{1/2}$$

$$\text{and } K = 6^{3/2} \phi_0 ((\bar{s}^2)_0 / M)^{3/2}$$

$$\text{and } (\bar{R}^2)_0^{1/2} = 6^{1/2} (\bar{s}^2)_0^{1/2}$$

In the present work, the unperturbed dimension has also been calculated from good solvent data by the application of different dilute solution theories.

The Flory-Fox-Schaeffgen equation³⁴ :

$$[\eta]^{2/3} M^{-1/3} = K^{2/3} + 2C_M(1/2 - \chi) K^{5/3} M[\eta]^{-1}$$

The Kurata and Stockmayer equation³⁵ :

$$[\eta]^{2/3} M^{-1/3} = K^{2/3} + 0.363 \phi_0 Bg(\alpha) M^{2/3} [\eta]^{-1/3}$$

The Stockmayer-Fixman equation³⁶ :

$$[\eta] M^{-1/2} = K + 0.5 \phi_0 B M^{1/3}$$

The unperturbed dimensions from the theta-solvent and from good solvent are arranged in Table 2. The theoretical equations show deviations from theta-solvent data only within the range of 30, which can be called rather a good agreement with the theta-solvent data.

Table 2

Method	Unperturbed dimension $([\bar{R}^2]_0 / M)^{1/2} \times 10^{11}$
Theta-solvent	754.895
Flory-Fox-Schaeffgen	758.710
Kurata-Stockmayer-Roig	774.921
Stockmayer-Fixman	780.504

The value of the unperturbed dimension of chlorosulfonated polyethylene is somewhat lower than polyisoprene³² of value $(810 \pm 45) \times 10^{-11}$ and polybutadiene³⁰ of value $(820 \pm 40) \times 10^{-11}$ but higher than polystyrene³⁷ of value $(670 \pm 15) \times 10^{-11}$ and quite similar in magnitude like polychloroprene³⁸ of value $(750 \pm 80) \times 10^{-11}$.

Experimental

Standard commercial sample of chlorosulfonated polyethylene (Hypalon 40) having Mooney viscosity (ML₄ at

100%) of 54, specific gravity 1.18, chlorine content 34.2% and sulfur content 0.95% was used. Commercially available toluene and methanol (AnalaR) were further dried and distilled before use. Details of fractionation, viscometry, and determination of $\bar{M}_w$ from light-scattering measurements in toluene, a non-theta solvent, have been described earlier¹⁹. A simple and rapid method for theta-composition, suggested by Elias, was used as reported earlier²¹.

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